

Interactive map of studies included in the Scoping Review on the influence of Urban Green Infrastructures on Vector-Borne Disease risk.

Urbanization is an ongoing global phenomenon that brings both opportunities and challenges. By 2050, approximately 70% of the world population is expected to live in urban areas. While urbanization helps to reduce inequalities and improve access to healthcare and education, it also raises significant environmental, climatic, human health and social challenges. Greening cities is recognized as a key intervention to "make cities inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable," as outlined by the United Nations (UN) Sustainable Development Goals (United Nations, 2022). Urban greening (Box 1) refers to the process of incorporating, developing, or preserving urban green infrastructures (UGIs) within urban environments through various initiatives. UGI (see Boxes 1 and 2) is an umbrella concept that includes a variety of elements such as blue spaces (e.g. lake, rivers and ponds (Hyseni et al., 2021)), green spaces (e.g. parks and green corridors, defined as interconnected landscape elements that help to protect the environment (Aly & Amer, 2010)), and urban forestry, including street and park trees. In this study, "greening" refers to the process itself, whereas "UGIs" denotes the tangible, physical components of urban nature that form the basis of greening efforts. As an illustration, Bowler *et al.* (2010) in a systematic review, examined the cooling effects of "greening type interventions", which are comparable to UGI elements such as urban parks and green roofs, on ground temperature relative to urban areas without vegetation. Substantial evidence highlights the positive impact of UGIs on human well-being and health. However, while urban green spaces provide ecological and health benefits, they may also create new habitats within cities that encourage the establishment and spread of arthropod vectors, invasive vertebrate species, or plants hosting exotic pathogens. This raises the risk of Vector-Borne Disease emergence and transmission in urban areas. Hematophagous (blood-feeding) arthropods are key players in transmitting zoonotic, veterinary, and economically significant pathogens.

To examine how urban green infrastructures influence VBD risks for humans, and animals, we conducted a scoping review following the 'Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses' (PRISMA) guidelines. One objective was to create an interactive world map to visualize the spatial distribution of all studies and their relevant elements.

A comprehensive search was conducted in October 2022 using three online databases: PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science. The search strategy combined key concepts related to "urban," "greening," "vector," and "vector-borne disease." All articles published up to October 6, 2022 (with no specified start date) were considered.

After the systematic database search, duplicates were automatically removed using CADIMA tools. The remaining articles underwent an initial systematic screening based on titles and abstracts, following these inclusion criteria: the articles (i) must be original research published in peer-reviewed journals in English; (ii) must address any aspect of the vector system (e.g., vector species, pathogens, or hosts); and (iii) articles must focus on at least one UGI (e.g., urban park, green/blue corridor, vegetation index or similar). Subsequently, a full-text screening was conducted to further refine the selection. Articles were included if they: (i) referred specifically to urban areas; (ii) examined any aspect of UGIs (e.g., urban parks, vegetation cover indices, or tree species); and (iii) statistically analyzed the effect of different UGIs (e.g., multiple parks, varying vegetation cover, or different tree species) on VBD risk including hazard, exposure, and/or vulnerability.

From each article, the following metadata was extracted: authors, DOI, locations (country, city), year of publication, vectors involved (e.g., groups such as mosquitoes, ticks, sandflies, chigger mites), including genus, as well as the associated disease, pathogen agent, and host of interest, when available. If an article included multiple countries and cities, all were extracted to ensure

comprehensive representation on the interactive map. However, only the first city was extracted for studies that mentioned several cities within the same country.

R version 4.2.3 (R Core Team, 2021) was used for the creation of the interactive map. The first step involved associating each city and country from every study with their corresponding longitude and latitude, which were extracted from Open Street Maps using the `osmdata` package (Padgham et al., 2017). Subsequently, the CSV file was converted into a geopackage format using the `sp` package (Pebesma, 2018). The interactive map, displaying metadata such as DOI, publication date, study locations, vectors, diseases, pathogen agents, and hosts (when available), was created using the `tmap` package (Tennekes, 2018). The script used for this process is available (« `Script_for_interactive_map.R` »). The interactive map is available (“`Interactive_Map_Greening_Cities_Vector_Risk.html`”). Every study that took place in different countries is represented, with different colors for every group of vectors. Ninety percent of the articles featured studies conducted in a single city and country.

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